

KEY CONTRIBUTING FACTORS AND COMMON METHODS OF CHEATING IN ONLINE EXAMINATIONS

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Abstract

The rapid shift to online education during the COVID-19 pandemic posed new challenges for ensuring academic integrity in university examinations. This study aims to identify the factors contributing to cheating and the methods employed by students during online examinations conducted for award of degrees and diplomas by higher education institutions. By conducting a survey on 450 people, those are the stack holders of online examination system comprising students, teachers and non-teaching staff having experience and knowledge about online examination system. Using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), the study extracted three major factors contributing to cheating: personal, environmental, and institutional factors. Also, the study identified a single dominant component Technologically-Enabled and Systemic Cheating Methods representing technological manipulation and unauthorized access as primary cheating method. The findings suggest the need for a unique an AI based online proctoring system and strict institutional policies to minimize academic dishonesty due to cheating in online examination. This study provides practical insights for educational institutions to enhance the integrity of online assessments.

Keywords: Online Examination, Academic Integrity, Cheating Behaviour, Online Proctoring Systems, Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

1. Introduction

The rise of online education has changed the traditional method of learning as well as the assessment method through which the physical examinations were conducted and assessments were made (Rüth, 2024). Cheating in online exams is a growing concern as institutions continue to transition to digital formats for assessments. Traditional exams are still favored by many due to the ease of supervising students and reducing academic dishonesty, which remains a critical issue in online settings (Peterson, 2019). Most of the universities have started Online Degree Programs through Online Distance Learning (ODL) mode. These courses are generally offered to students at remote locations and all the teaching activities and the assessments are made online. The examinations for such courses are conducted through online mode via proctored examination system. Most of the universities and boards have also conducted exams of their regular degree programs in online mode through the proctor based online examination system during the Covid-19 pandemic (Henry, 2022; Knox, 2021). Students feel anxiety and kind of stress due to continuous monitoring in

online proctoring systems and this can hamper their performance (Woldeab & Brothen, 2019). Different kind of cheating activities and flag suspicious behavior and unauthorized access to cheating material or mobile phones uses are captured using technologies like webcams, microphones, and secure browsers (Slusky, 2020; Milone et al., 2017). Students may exploit different kinds of technical issues such as poor internet connectivity, giving rise for the need for robust systems to ensure fairness (Ilgaz & AfacanAdanır, 2020). Students privacy concern and ethical issues arise due to the extensive data collection and monitoring practices of proctoring systems, thus gives rise for a balanced data collection that maintains academic integrity and protecting students' privacy (Coghlan et al., 2020). However, the actual scale of cheating remains unclear, with less attention given to this form of misconduct compared to others like plagiarism (Garg & Goel, 2022).

The online examination system has offered flexibility and convenience to the remote learners but it has also raised the activities of academic dishonesty like cheating in inline exams. The academic integrity of the institution has undermined due to cheating activities and compromises the validity of assessment outcomes. The different types and methods of cheating are important to understand and developing effective cheating detection and prevention strategies that may enhance the academic integrity of the institutions awarding the degrees.

1.1. Problem Statement

The online examination provide an easy and alternative method to conduct the examination in place of physical or in-person test but these are susceptible to different forms of cheating as the proper supervision is not there and in a familiar place of the examinee where the unauthorized material can be accessed easily. There are various factors like improper proctoring, pressure of getting good grades; society value, fear of future etc. may contribute to cheating (Noorbehbahani et al., 2022). Different kind of cheating techniques like technological tools, written/ printed material, server hacking etc. are used by the students in online examination (Slusky, 2020; Milone et al., 2017). However, the factors and techniques of cheating may vary according to location, technological advancements, type of environment etc. but there are limited empirical research have been conducted to analyze and determine the factors and techniques of cheating in online examinations conducted by universities in India. The present research is conducted to examine these factors and techniques of cheating in online examination examinations conducted for award of degrees by the universities in India.

1.2. Research Objectives

The present study focus on the following objectives in context to cheating in online examinations:

- I. To identify the factors that contributes to cheating in online examinations.
- II. To determine the methods and extent of cheating in online examinations.

2 Literature Review

Recent studies on cheating in online exams have highlighted various methods students use to gain an unfair advantage, including accessing unauthorized materials, using additional devices for online searches, collaborating with others, and outsourcing the exam to someone else (Noorbehbahani et al., 2022). Dawson (2020) defines e-cheating as 'cheating that uses or is enabled by technology,' which poses a significant threat to the validity of online examinations. Various factors like fear of failure, peer pressure, the perception that others are cheating, and the ease with which cheating can be done, works as motivators of cheating (Noorbehbahani et al., 2022). During the COVID-19 pandemic, according to reports, cheating activities and plagiarism became more prevalent as online assessments are frequent and universities struggle to ensure the security and integrity of these exams (Henry, 2022; Knox, 2021).

2.1. Causes of Cheating:

Newton et al. (2023) highlight the long-term challenge of cheating and dishonesty in online examinations, a problem that arise due to the significant increase of remote learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study identified that various opportunities for cheating and dishonesty are available in online exam formats, making students more likely to engage in individual cheating behaviors. Siaputra (2013) and Wallace and Newton (2014) concluded that academic cheating behavior majorly caused due to ineffective time management and procrastination, as students oftentry to cheat for making up with looming deadlines and poor preparation of the examination. Husain et al. (2017) identified that students engage in cheating activities due to their perception about institutional apathy toward academic integrity. Brimble (2016) summarized that students can engage in cheating activities for meeting the academic demands caused by high expectations from universities, and external personal pressure.

Bretag et al. (2018) and Moss et al. (2018) suggest that different factors, causes students to engage in cheating activities, like unhealthy learning environment, including negative experiences or a lack of engagement. Barbaranelli et al. (2018) concluded that competition with the peers for performance in examination generally motivates the students to engage in cheating behaviors. Sevnarayan and Maphoto (2024) concluded that cheating behaviors are proportional to the cognitive abilities of the students, the learning progress of the students and management abilities of their learning processes.

2.2. Findings from similar studies

Henderson et al. (2022) conducted a large-scale study at an Australian university during the Covid-19 lockdowns in 2021 on 7,839 students who appeared for online examination. The study concluded that 216 students were admitted to cheating, different factors were identified that potentially influenced their behavior. Cheating cases were less frequent but varied across various contexts, irrespective of security measures, kinds of assessments, exam time and conditions, and personal characteristics of the students.

Genereux and McLeod (1995) concluded that offline pan paper based traditional exams can reach as high as 51.8% cheating rates, while Chapman et al. (2004) found that about 24% cheating rates, showing variability across studies.

Dyer et al. (2020), Jenkins et al. (2022), and Pleasants et al. (2022) report significantly higher rates of cheating in online exams, with figures reaching 62%, 58.4%, and 70%, respectively, highlighting the distinct challenges associated with maintaining academic integrity in remote assessment environments.

2. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The present study comes under “exploratory cum descriptive research design” as the research aims to investigate and explore the different types of cheating in online examination system of universities. The research study also aims to find various methods of cheating in online examination and answers about the depth of cheating in real time online examination system.

The online examination conducted for award of degree by universities or boards has large number of cheating cases and unfair academic means, present study is conducted to gain insights on the cheating scenario. Hence, the target population are the stack holders of the university examination system that include students, teachers, research scholars and non-teaching staff engaged in conduct of online examination system.

The study utilized a purposive sampling method to select respondents, focusing on individuals directly involved in online examinations, such as students, teachers, research scholars and staff involved in conduct of online examination. This sampling technique was chosen to ensure that participants possessed relevant knowledge and experience regarding the types, methods, and extent of cheating in online exams. By targeting these specific groups, the study aimed to gather insights from those most familiar with the phenomenon under investigation, thereby enhancing the reliability and relevance of the data collected through the questionnaires.

The research study aims to answer the research questions by taking inputs from the respondents through a questionnaire. The questionnaire developed for collection of primary data from the stack holders of online examination system has been divided into two sections according to the research questions. There are total 14 questions in two sections of the questionnaire based on 5 likert scale (1 for Strongly Agree; 2 for Agree; 3 for Can't say; 4 for Disagree and 5 for Strongly Disagree) and two open ended questions are given as to accept opinions of respondents about any missing term that is not considered at the researcher side. The questionnaire has been developed using Google form and forwarded through e-mail to 520 respondents, out of which 450 respondents have recorded their responses. The data collection period was from September 10, 2024 to December 30, 2024.

3.2. Research Tools

The research has been conducted using different technological tools. The data collection process has been completed using a research questionnaire developed in Google's cloud platform 'forms'. The responses gathered through questionnaire are concluded in a MS Excel file. Data analysis of the collected responses has been performed using SPSS software. The text format responses are converted to numerical data for using as SPSS input file. The original variables relating to corresponding research objective has been considered for analysis using SPSS software.

3.3. Respondents Profile

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents who participated in the study. A total of 450 respondents have responded, with background information across various categories such as age, education level, experience with online examinations, and occupation.

Table 1: Demographic information of the respondents

		Number and Percentage
Age-group	Under 18	23
	18-24	328
	25-34	64
	35-44	32
	45 or above	03
Education	Bachelor's Degree	208
	Master's Degree	216
	Ph.D.	26
Experience in Online Examinations	Yes, As observer/ flying squad member	15
	Yes, As superintendent/ invigilator	18
	Yes, As examinee/ student	240
	No, I have no experience of online exam but I know about it	151
	Neither I have experience of online exam nor I know about it	26
Occupation	Student	371
	Research Scholar	14
	Teacher	46
	Non-Teaching Staff	19

3.4. Age Group

The age distribution of respondents have been considered to find out the curiosity to cheat at different maturity level, with 328 respondents (72.89%) falling in the 18-24 age group. This is followed by 64 respondents (14.22%) in the 25-34 age group. Smaller numbers were found in the under 18 (23 participant, 5.11%), 35-44 (32 participants, 7.11%), and 45 or above (3 participants, 0.67%) categories. The study has higher percentage on younger participants, as they are more familiar with online educational platforms.

3.5. Education Level

Respondents having different qualifications are considered as, 208 participants (46.22%) are graduates. A significantly larger proportion, 226 participants (48%), are post graduates, and 26 participants (5.78%) are Ph.D. degree holders. This highlights that the sample taken for study is having participants with qualification of at least bachelor's degree as most of those are having experience of online examination.

3.6. Online Examinations Experience

The respondents' experience with online examinations has varied, as major of respondents are directly involved as examinees. In the sample taken for present study, 240 participants (53.33%) had enrolled as examinees during their study, 15 respondents (3%) had experience of working as observer members of a flying squad in online exams, while 18 participants (4%) had served as invigilators. A total of 151 respondents (34%) were no direct experience but were familiar with online exams that show their awareness about online examination formats. The sample also included 26 respondents (6%) having no experience and any knowledge of online exams.

3.7. Occupation

The sample taken for present study included students as majority of participants as 371 respondents (82%) identifying as students. A small number of research scholars (14 participants, 3%), teachers (46 participants, 11%), and non-teaching staff (19 participants, 4%). The high representation of students justifies the focus of the study on individuals who are actively engaged in academic environments, particularly in online examination system opted by their universities.

4 Data Analysis

Data analysis of the primary data collected through questionnaire has been performed in two phases as per the requirement of the research objectives. The first research objective is to determine the factors leading to cheat in online examinations and the factor analysis report for the research question.

4.1. Factor Analysis of Cheating Factors in Online Examinations

The research objective of the study aims to identify the factors that contribute to cheating in online examinations as well as the common methods that are used for cheating; factor analysis has been performed on the primary data collected through questionnaire.

4.1.1. Suitability of Data for Factor Analysis

To assess whether the dataset was appropriate for factor analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s test of sphericity were conducted.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Data Set of Cheating Factors

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.704
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	191.093
	Df	28
	Sig.	.000

The KMO value was 0.704, indicating a moderate level of sampling adequacy, which is considered acceptable for factor analysis. Bartlett’s test of sphericity yielded a significant result ($\chi^2 = 191.093$, $df = 28$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that there were sufficient correlations among the variables to justify the use of factor analysis.

4.1.2. Communalities and Factor Extraction for Cheating in Online Examinations

Communalities represent the proportion of each variable’s variance that is explained by the extracted factors. High communalities (above 0.5) suggest that a variable is well-represented in the factor solution, while lower values indicate weaker representation. The extraction communalities for the variables ranged from 0.360 to 0.815. Notably, the variable Difficult Questions had the highest communality (0.815), suggesting that this factor plays a significant role in the cheating behavior of students. Other strongly represented variables include Mental Pressure (0.698) and Lack of Online Monitoring (0.501). On the other hand, variables such as Not Prepared for Exam (0.360) and Lack of Punishment Rules (0.418) had lower communalities, indicating that these may have a weaker influence or require further investigation.

4.1.3. Total Variance Explained for Factors of Cheating in Online Examinations

The factor analysis extracted three key components that explained a cumulative variance of 55.784%, suggesting that these three factors adequately represent the underlying structure of cheating behavior in online exams.

Table 3: Total variance and component extraction through PCA

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.249	28.116	28.116	2.249	28.116	28.116	1.858	23.226	23.226
2	1.147	14.340	42.457	1.147	14.340	42.457	1.532	19.150	42.377
3	1.066	13.327	55.784	1.066	13.327	55.784	1.073	13.407	55.784

4	.893	11.164	66.948						
5	.765	9.564	76.512						
6	.673	8.406	84.919						
7	.631	7.889	92.808						
8	.575	7.192	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

The first factor accounted for 28.116% of the variance, the second factor explained 14.340%, and the third factor contributed 13.327%. The scree plot and eigen value criterion (>1) supported retaining these three components for further analysis.

Fig. 1. Scree plot (Eigen values vs Component Number)

The scree plot shows that the component 1 has clearly shown that the curve decrease and flattens after the first three components and all the remaining components have eigen value less than one. The further analysis has been done considering these three components.

4.1.4. Rotated Component Matrix

To better interpret the factors, Varimax rotation was applied, which simplifies the factor structure by maximizing the variance of loadings for each component.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix

Original Factors	Component		
	1	2	3
Ethical values	.534	.316	-.289
Not Prepared for Exam	.570	.182	.031
More Marks from Peers	.132	.717	.106
Lack of Online Monitoring	.703	.068	-.042
Difficult Questions	.067	.183	.881
Mental Pressure	.051	.833	.048

Lack of Punishment Rules	.432	.368	-.309
Lackadaisical attitude	.736	-.136	.317

The rotated component matrix shows correlations between variable and factor. Principal Component Analysis(PCA)extraction method has been used for component extraction andVarimax with Kaiser Normalization method has been used for rotation. The rotation overall converged in six iterations.

4.1.5. Component TransformationMatrix

The component transformation matrix confirmed that the rotated solution was well-structured, with the first component having the highest correlation with the original solution (0.804), followed by the second component (0.771) and the third component (0.963). This indicates that the rotated factors adequately represent distinct dimensions of cheating behavior.

4.2. Factor Analysis of Cheating Methods in Online Examinations

Factor analysis was conducted to identify the underlying structure among different cheating methods in online examinations. The analysis aimed to determine whether these methods could be grouped into a single component or multiple components and how much variance each factor explains.

4.2.1. KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity shows the following results about the suitability of the dataset for the analysis of various cheating methods in online examination.

Table 5: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Data Set of Cheating Methods

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.843	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	497.718
	Df	15
	Sig.	.000

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure = 0.843 value is considered meritorious, indicating that the dataset is well-suited for factor analysis about cheating methods in online examinations.Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2 = 497.718$, $df = 15$, $p < 0.001$)and significant p-value (0.000) suggests that there are adequate correlations between variables, justifying the use of factor analysis.

4.2.2. Communalities of Cheating Methods in Online Examinations

Communalities indicate how much of each variable's variance is explained by the extracted factor. Higher communalities (closer to 1) suggest a stronger association with the extracted factor.

Table 6: Extracted Factors for Cheating Methods

Variable	Initial	Extraction
Online Resources (Internet)	1.000	0.138
Unauthorized Devices	1.000	0.578
Impersonation	1.000	0.607
Hacking of Servers	1.000	0.651
Accessing the Paper Remotely	1.000	0.642
Seating Arrangement	1.000	0.580

The result shows that Hacking of Servers (0.651), Impersonation (0.607), and Accessing Paper Remotely (0.642) have high extraction values, meaning they strongly contribute to the extracted component. Online Resources (Internet) has a low extraction value (0.138), indicating a weak relationship with the extracted factor.

4.2.3. Total Variance Explained for Methods of Cheating in Online Examinations

The Total Variance Explained table provides insights into how much variance each component accounts for.

Table 7: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Data Set of Cheating Factors

Component	Initial Eigenvalues	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings
1	3.195 (53.257%)	3.195 (53.257%)
2	0.940 (15.667%)	-
3	0.557 (9.279%)	-
4	0.521 (8.680%)	-
5	0.447 (7.446%)	-
6	0.340 (5.372%)	-

Only one factor was extracted, explaining 53.257% of the total variance. Since only one factor had an eigen value greater than 1, other components were not retained and only the single component under which various variables grouped has been used for analysis.

4.2.4. Component Matrix

The role of each variable (Factor Loading) for cheating methods in the extracted component has been displayed by the Component Matrix.

Table 8: Factor Loading for Variables of Cheating Methods

Variable	Component 1 Loading
Online Resources (Internet)	0.372
Unauthorized Devices	0.760
Impersonation	0.779
Hacking of Servers	0.807
Accessing the Paper Remotely	0.801
Seating Arrangement	0.761

The three major contributors are Hacking of Servers (0.807), Impersonation (0.779), and Accessing Paper Remotely (0.801) as shown in the table. The main component is weakly associated with the variable Online Resources (Internet) as it has lowest loading (0.372).

4.2.5. Interpretation

The combined component encompasses various cheating techniques into one factor, which represents 53.26% of the variance in the cheating methods, emphasizing the technological and procedural gaps that prove advantageous for the students cheating during online examinations. The factor loading matrix indicates that "Hacking of Servers" (0.807), "Accessing the Paper Remotely" (0.801), "Impersonation" (0.779), and "Unauthorized Devices" (0.760) demonstrated the highest loadings, suggesting a strong correlation among these cheating methods. The connection between Online Resources (Internet) and the factor is weak, indicating that it might not be a major method of cheating in this dataset. The findings indicate that loopholes in digital setup and external resources are exploited by the students to engage in cheating practices during online examinations and technological and strategic cheating methods are the most prominent, suggesting the need for updated and modern security measures in online examinations.

3. Result and Discussion

5.1. The results of the factor analysis for the factors of cheating in online examination

Three major factors of cheating in online examinations including ‘institutional and procedural weaknesses’, ‘social and psychological pressures’, and ‘examination difficulty’ has been discovered by present study. Different factor groups were identified by the rotated component matrix. The names of the group have been given according to the communalities covered by factor. The grouping of communalities with the level of correlation with the factor is shown below. The resulted factors are:

Factor 1: Institutional and Procedural Weaknesses

The correlation of the four communalities as ‘Lack of Online Monitoring (0.703)’, ‘Lackadaisical Attitude (0.736)’, ‘Ethical Values (0.534)’, and ‘Lack of Punishment Rules (0.432)’ constituted the first factor and names as Institutional and Procedural Weaknesses.

The findings suggested that institutional weaknesses compose ineffective monitoring and lenient punishment policies, give significant rise to students cheating behavior. Ethical issues also play a role, as a weak moral value among students may produce academic dishonesty.

Factor 2: Social and Psychological Pressures

The three communalities including 'More Marks from Peers (0.717)', 'Mental Pressure (0.833)', and 'Not Prepared for Exam (0.570)' grouped together to form the second factor and named as Social and Psychological Pressures.

The outside pressure on the student like 'peer influence' and 'academic stresses' might lead students to engage in dishonest practices. Variables like 'Anxiety' and 'Fear of failure' contribute in student's decision to cheat as suggested by the loading of 'Mental Pressure'.

Factor 3: Examination Difficulty

A Factor '*Difficult Questions* (0.881)' is a single dominant variable, suggesting that the difficulty level of questions asked and as perceived by the students is a standalone factor that may give rise to students interest for cheating. Students may resort to dishonest means to secure better results when they find questions asked as excessively challenging.

5.2. The factor analysis for the methods of cheating in online examination

Different cheating methods used by the students for cheating in online examinations may be encapsulated in a singular latent construct as per concluded by the present study. This construct basically encapsulates the unauthorized technological interventions, like 'hacking of server', 'impersonation', and 'use of external devices'.

Factor 1: Technologically-Enabled and Systemic Cheating Methods

The extracted factor revealed advanced and system-based cheating techniques enabled by technology and examination loopholes as different cheating methods (e.g., use of unauthorized devices, impersonation, hacking, remote access, and seating arrangements) are loaded onto a single component and named as Technologically-Enabled and Systemic Cheating Methods. The results conclude that there is only one major factor which leads to major cheating methods employed by the students during the online examination.

4. Conclusion and Future Scope

The present study investigated the factors contributing to cheating and the methods of cheating employed by students to cheat in online university examinations. Three distinct factors were identified concerning the contributors to cheating: personal factors, environmental factors, and institutional factors; through Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Personal factors included variables like 'student's ethical values', 'less preparation for examination', and 'mental pressure'. The environmental factors included variables like 'lack of online monitoring' and 'punishment rules'. Institutional factors included variables such as 'lenient punishment policies' and 'lackadaisical attitude of the invigilators' that played a critical role in encouraging dishonest behaviors.

Regarding methods employed for cheating by the students, the study found that all six cheating methods including ‘hacking of servers’, ‘impersonation’, ‘use of unauthorized devices’ and ‘remote access to examination papers’ loaded significantly onto a single component and names as Technologically-Enabled and Systemic Cheating Methods. The findings suggested that cheating and unfair means generally exploits the technological loopholes and breach the ineffective security measures in online examinations.

Higher education institutions may directly imply the results of the present study as the results are compiled on sample of graduates and more qualified population. Strengthening online proctoring mechanisms, implementing robust cyber security policies, and promoting academic integrity awareness are most important for conducting online examinations.

These results suggest that universities should improve their online and remote proctoring mechanisms, establish strict academic integrity policies, and provide ethical means and mental health support to remove academic cheating and unfair means. Further, the results also suggest that examination difficulty of moderate and low level and fairer assessment strategies may reduce unwanted stress on students that help in reducing the commonness of cheating in online examinations.

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